

OPTIMIZATION OF A VEHICLE MOUNT PROJECT VIA A PRIMAL-DUAL INTERIOR-POINT ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

The mount project is extremely important to ensure good isolation of equipment that generates vibration, be it a motor, a hydraulic pump, a compressor, among others. For the mount project, the positioning of the mount and its stiffness are very important characteristics, as they influence the independence of the moving directions and also the isolation performance. For the application of mount project in powertrains, this is not different, as the high isolation performance of the mount is extremely important to ensure the reduction of vibration transmission from the powertrain and, for this, the stiffness of the mount and its attachment point must be adequately selected. Another important factor in the mount project is the modal purity, which quantifies the decoupling between the degrees of freedom, and the greater the modal purity, the greater the decoupling of each degree of freedom in each direction. This is important to reduce the vibrational effects transmitted from a given force in a given direction and also for better control of the vibrational distribution of the system. To describe the modal purity, it is necessary to have information on the natural frequencies and vibration modes of the powertrain suspended on the mounts. To evaluate the isolation performance, the stiffness and damping of the mount must be carefully determined to ensure good isolation. In this work, analytical solutions are developed taking into account the parameters of stiffness, mount damping, mount position, mount angle, mass and the inertia tensor. With these analytical solutions, it was possible to develop an optimization process using optimization algorithms with the objective of finding the parameters that generate high vibrational isolation performance and high modal purity. After optimization significant improvements were observed. The modal purity of each degree of freedom was generally higher than 85%, whereas, before optimization, there were modal purities below 50%. While the most common approach is to work only with the stiffness to meet the modal purity and the mount isolation performance this work expands and investigate deeper the potential to improve these parameters including the mount position in this optimization iteration process.

Keywords: Mount; Powertrain; Isolation; Modal Purity; Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

The effect and perception of vibration have always been relevant in the operation of dynamic systems. This relevance has led to the development and application of vibration analysis to prevent unforeseen issues. For instance, vibration analysis is widely used in predictive maintenance, enabling the diagnosis of faults—especially in their early stages—thereby reducing cost impact and supporting decision-making to prevent critical issues [1].

Many material studies have been conducted—and continue to be—to improve the efficiency of vibration isolation. One example is the use of metamaterials, which are meticulously designed at the micro- or nano-scale to enhance vibration isolation performance [2].

There are two types of isolation systems for mounts. The first type of isolation is passive, in which techniques using rubber elements or mechanical springs are used. Isolation is achieved by limiting the capacity of vibration transmitted from the source to the structure to be isolated. This is done through a mechanical connection that dissipates or redirects the vibration energy before it reaches the structure to

be isolated. Passive methods sometimes involve electromechanical controls to adjust the system, but the isolation mechanism is passive. Passive systems are economical, and their relative simplicity makes them more reliable and safer. Elastomers used in the automotive industry to isolate powertrains are one of the most used passive isolators. Additionally, passive isolation systems also offer good performance, low cost, high reliability, and relative simplicity. The second type of isolation is active isolation, which consists of an insulating material, for example, hydraulic fluid, a vibration sensor, an electronic circuit, and an actuator. The vibration from the powertrain is read by the vibration sensor, which transmits the information to the electronic circuit, which calculates in real-time the necessary displacement compensation. This displacement compensation is transmitted to the actuator to cancel the vibrations. The performance of active isolators is superior to that of passive actuators; however, cost and complexity issues hinder their application.

Despite these technical differences in isolation technologies, the physical parameters to obtain a high isolation performance are the same.

The isolation performance is a complex study because it varies according to the frequency and the interactions of the mount and the fixation also plays a critical role in the isolation performance. One of the things that contribute to the performance of the mount project is the modal purity because it implies that once some direction is excited the other will not be if the modal purity is high. The Experimental Modal Analysis (EMA) is used to study many structural properties, one of them being the modal purity [3]. The EMA technique can be applied to evaluate the rigid body modes of the powertrain, which can induce low-frequency vibration when excited by the track or from the powertrain itself if the modal purity is low [4].

The effectiveness of a mount project's isolation performance is not limited to modal purity. It is influenced by factors such as dynamic stiffness, local modes of the metal part of the mount, mass-spring mode of the rubber or isolator material, load variation, etc. All these parameters cause the isolation to change across different frequencies.

Therefore, it is important to have robust virtual models, effective measurement methodologies, and practical experience to properly consider the variables that influence isolation performance and determine which changes should be made to improve the mount project.

Currently, optimization tools have been used in different applications of science and are powerful in solving many complex problems with effective results concerning time and performance, so within this context, optimization tools are used in this work to explore the mount project aiming to define the variables that result in the best performance within certain restrictions that are imposed by the criterion of the mount project.

The chapter II of this work presents the analytical model of a generic mount system of six DOF and the math approach to build it and the methodology used to apply the optimization process. It also shows in more detail the principles of the algorithm used to carry out the optimization of the developed objective function.

In Chapter III the optimization results are presented. Different initial conditions of the algorithm are tested to verify if there is variation in the optimum vector and how big it is.

Chapter IV presents the conclusions and findings of the work. Possibilities for future works are discussed as well.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the optimization concepts used to solve the addressed problem are presented. A brief overview of constrained optimization theory and some fundamentals of vibration used to define the problem is provided.

The optimization algorithm employed is based on interior-point using the primal-dual logarithmic barrier method, which can accommodate both equality and inequality constraints. However, in the problem considered in this work, only inequality constraints will be applied.

2.1. Mathematical Model of Six DOF of the Motor Fixed with Mounts

For a system of MDOFs with hysteretic damping, with N degrees of freedom, the governing equations of motion can be written in matrix form as:

$$[\mathbf{M}]\{\ddot{\mathbf{R}}\} + [\mathbf{K}]\{\mathbf{R}\} + i[\mathbf{H}_k]\{\mathbf{R}\} = \{\mathbf{F}\}, \quad (1)$$

where $[\mathbf{H}_k]$ is the matrix of hysteretic damping [5]. Considering the free vibration solution by setting $\{\mathbf{F}\} = 0$ is possible to determine the natural modal properties of the system. Under this condition, a displacement solution for Eq. (1) is of the form $\{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}\} = \{\mathbf{R}\} e^{i\lambda t}$.

Substituting these conditions into Eq. (1), we arrive at the following expression.

$$([\mathbf{K}_c] - \omega^2[\mathbf{M}])\{\mathbf{R}\} = \{0\}, \quad (2)$$

where $[\mathbf{K}_c] = [\mathbf{K}] + i[\mathbf{H}_k]$ and $[\mathbf{K}_c]$ is formed by the sum of each mount stiffness in the global coordinate system.

$$[\mathbf{K}_c] = \sum_{i=1}^N [\mathbf{B}_i]^T [\mathbf{k}_i]_G [\mathbf{B}_i]. \quad (3)$$

where $[\mathbf{B}_i] = [[\mathbf{I}] [\mathbf{H}_i]]$ and $[\mathbf{H}_i]$ is defined as a skew-matrix of the mount position i [6].

$$[\mathbf{H}_i] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & r_{iz} & -r_{iy} \\ -r_{iz} & 0 & r_{ix} \\ r_{iy} & -r_{ix} & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The only non-trivial solution of Eq. (2) is given by:

$$\det([\mathbf{K}_c] - \omega^2[\mathbf{M}]) = 0. \quad (5)$$

From the solution of the Eq. (5), it is obtained the diagonal matrix of eigenvalues $[\lambda_r^2]$ and eigenvectors $[\Psi]$ that form the modal model, but now both the eigenvalues and eigenvectors belong to the set of complex numbers. Here, the eigenvalue λ_r^2 is the r -th eigenvalue and has the following form:

$$\lambda_r^2 = \omega_r^2(1 + i\eta_r). \quad (6)$$

Considering the case where external sinusoidal forces are applied $\{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}\} = \{\mathbf{F}\}e^{i\omega t}$, all of the same frequency, ω , but with different amplitudes and phases, and similarly, we assume a response of the form $\{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}\}_G = \{\mathbf{R}\}_G e^{i\omega t}$, we can write the inverse of the receptance matrix.

$$([\mathbf{K}_c] - \omega^2[\mathbf{M}]) = [\alpha(\omega)]^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

Multiplying both sides with the eigenvectors leads to:

$$[(\lambda_r^2 - \omega^2)] = [\Phi]^T [\alpha(\omega)]^{-1} [\Phi]. \quad (8)$$

This results in:

$$[\alpha(\omega)] = [\Phi][(\lambda_r^2 - \omega^2)]^{-1} [\Phi]^T. \quad (9)$$

Therefore, each term $\alpha_{jk}(\omega)$ for the hysteretic modal model is given by

$$\alpha_{jk}(\omega) = \sum_{r=1}^N \frac{(\phi_{jr})(\phi_{kr})}{\omega_r^2 - \omega^2 + i\eta_r \omega_r^2}. \quad (10)$$

From Eq. (10) the FRFs of the hysteretic model can be calculated using again the mass normalized eigenvectors, however now the hysteresis will generate a phase and the numerator and denominator are complex numbers.

2.2. Optimization

The goal of the optimization is to identify a point that minimizes a function, subject to equality and/or inequality constraints, as described by [7]. In mathematical terms, an optimization problem is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Minimize } f(\{\mathbf{X}\}) \\ & \text{Such that: } h_j(\{\mathbf{X}\}) = 0; j = 1 \text{ to } p \\ & \quad g_i(\{\mathbf{X}\}) \leq 0; i = 1 \text{ to } m, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\{\mathbf{X}\}$ represents the set (vector) of the design variables (the parameters that can be change during the optimization process), f denotes the objective function, h_j corresponds to the equality constraints, and g_i to the inequality constraints.

There are some techniques to solve the problem of Eq. (11) and one of the them is the interior-point using the primal-dual logarithmic barrier method (PDLB) [8] which is considered a robust and efficient approach.

In the PDLB method, the inequality constraints from Eq. (11) are transformed into equalities by introducing positive slack variables s_i . This leads to the modified problem presented in Eq. (12)

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Minimize } f(\{\mathbf{X}\}) \\ & \text{Such that: } h_j(\{\mathbf{X}\}) = 0; j = 1 \text{ to } p \\ & \quad g_i(\{\mathbf{X}\}) + s_i = 0; i = 1 \text{ to } m. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Subsequently, a logarithmic barrier function is added to the objective function to ensure the non-negativity of the slack variables, as shown in equation

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Miminimize } f(\{\mathbf{X}\}) - \mu \sum_i \ln(s_i) \\ & \text{Such that: } h_j(\{\mathbf{X}\}) = 0; j = 1 \text{ to } p \\ & \quad g_i(\{\mathbf{X}\}) + s_i = 0; i = 1 \text{ to } m, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where μ is referred to as the barrier parameter and the $\ln(s_i)$ is called the logarithmic barrier function.

Thus, the following logarithmic barrier Lagrangian function is obtained:

$$L(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}) = f(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}) + \mu \sum_{i=1}^m \ln(s_i) + \sum_{i=1}^m u_{k,i} \nabla^2 g_i(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}) + \sum_{i=1}^p v_{k,i} \nabla^2 h_i(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}). \quad (14)$$

The necessary condition of first order is applied to the barrier Lagrangian logarithmic barrier function Eq. (14), resulting in a system of nonlinear equations (3.16):

$$\nabla L(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}) = \begin{bmatrix} \nabla f(\{\mathbf{X}\}) + [\mathbf{J}_h]^T \{\mathbf{v}\} + [\mathbf{J}_g]^T \{\mathbf{u}\} \\ \{\mathbf{u}\} - \mu \{\mathbf{s}\}^{-1} \\ \{\mathbf{h}(\{\mathbf{X}\})\} \\ \{\mathbf{g}(\{\mathbf{X}\})\} + \{\mathbf{s}\} \end{bmatrix} = 0, \quad (15)$$

here $[\mathbf{J}_g]$ denotes the Jacobian of the constraint functions $\{\mathbf{g}(\{\mathbf{X}\})\}$ and $[\mathbf{J}_h]$ denotes the Jacobian of the constraint functions $\{\mathbf{h}(\{\mathbf{X}\})\}$.

The solution of the nonlinear system is given by the Newton's Method [9] as in Eq (16)

$$[\mathbf{W}] \Delta \{\mathbf{d}\} = -\nabla L(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}), \quad (16)$$

where $\Delta \{\mathbf{d}\}^T = (\Delta \{\mathbf{X}\}, \Delta \{\mathbf{s}\}, \Delta \{\mathbf{u}\}, \Delta \{\mathbf{v}\})$ and $[\mathbf{W}]$ is given by

$$[\mathbf{W}] = \begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{H}] & 0 & [\mathbf{J}_h]^T & [\mathbf{J}_g]^T \\ 0 & -\mu[\mathbf{S}]^{-1} & 0 & [\mathbf{I}] \\ [\mathbf{J}_h] & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ [\mathbf{J}_g] & [\mathbf{I}] & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

$[\mathbf{H}]$ is referred to as the Hessian matrix of the Lagrangian function where:

$$[\mathbf{H}] = \nabla_{xx}^2 L(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}) = \nabla^2 f(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}) + \sum_{i=1}^m u_{k,i} \nabla^2 g_i(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}) + \sum_{i=1}^p v_{k,i} \nabla^2 h_i(\{\mathbf{X}_k\}). \quad (18)$$

And the submatrix $[\mathbf{S}]$ is give by

$$[\mathbf{S}] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\mu}{(s_1)^2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\mu}{(s_m)^2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

The vector of the variables $\{\mathbf{X}\}$, $\{\mathbf{s}\}$, $\{\mathbf{u}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{v}\}$ are updated according to

$$\begin{aligned} \{\mathbf{X}_{k+1}\} &= \{\mathbf{X}_k\} + \alpha_p \Delta\{\mathbf{X}_k\} \\ \{\mathbf{s}_{k+1}\} &= \{\mathbf{s}_k\} + \alpha_p \Delta\{\mathbf{s}_k\} \\ \{\mathbf{v}_{k+1}\} &= \{\mathbf{v}_k\} + \alpha_d \Delta\{\mathbf{v}_k\} \\ \{\mathbf{u}_{k+1}\} &= \{\mathbf{u}_k\} + \alpha_d \Delta\{\mathbf{u}_k\}, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

For further details of the determination of α_p and α_d [10] and [11] can be used as reference for deeper understanding.

2.3. Definition of the Objective Function, Design Variables and Constraints

The global stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{K}_c]$ has a mount position dependence, because $[\mathbf{K}_c] = \sum_{i=1}^N [\mathbf{B}_i]^T [\mathbf{k}_i]_G [\mathbf{B}_i]$.

The optimization of the vibrational isolation performance of the motor of this work is formed by four mounts. The three directions of each mount stiffness will be explored in this work, as there are four mounts then a total of twelve stiffness variables will compose the problem, furthermore, two mount positions will be variable whereas the other two mounts will be fixed. The three directions of the two mount positions which are subject to optimizations will be explored, so altogether eighteen variables will be subjected to the optimization process.

The Eq. (23) shows the 26N constrained functions, where g_1 up to g_8 are related to the modal purity of the six DOF, the frequency mode distribution and the mount transmissibility. The constrained functions from g_9 up to g_{14} are related to the position of mounts 1 and 2. The constrained functions from g_{15} up to g_{26} are related to the stiffness of the mounts 1 to 4.

The objective function is built to meet the criterion of high modal purity, which is based on the high contribution of the vector component of each eigenvector.

The modal purity P_{kr} , as described by [12], is given by the kinetic energy, which is associated with each mode shape, and is given by the kinetic energy of each mode as

$$P_{kr} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^6 M_{kj} \phi_{kr} \phi_{jr}}{\sum_{k=1}^6 \sum_{j=1}^6 M_{kj} \phi_{kr} \phi_{jr}} \times 100\%. \quad (21)$$

The term M_{kj} is the mass element of the matrix $[\mathbf{M}]$, ϕ_{kr} and ϕ_{jr} are the elements of the eigenvector matrix $[\mathbf{\Psi}]$ and then P_{kr} represents the kinetic energy of the r -th mode at the k -th DOF.

The eigenvector comes from the matrix $[\mathbf{M}]$ and the global stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{K}_c]$. This matrix $[\mathbf{K}_c]$ has a mount position dependence, because $[\mathbf{K}_c] = \sum_{i=1}^N [\mathbf{B}_i]^T [\mathbf{k}_i]_G [\mathbf{B}_i]$. For this reason, the elements of

the eigenvector matrix $[\Psi]$ are affected by the mount position and as consequence the modal purity, which is dependent of the elements of the matrix $[\Psi]$ are dependent on the mount position as well. The objective function is given by the sum of the maximum value of each P_{kr} of each r -th mode:

$$f(\{X\}) = - \sum_{k=1}^6 \sum_{r=1}^6 \max(P_{kr}). \quad (22)$$

In Eq. (22), the minus sign is used because the algorithm is designed to search for the minimum value of $f(\{X\})$, thus, minimizing $f(\{X\})$ is equivalent to maximizing the $-f(\{X\})$. The minimum value $f(\{X\})$ can achieve is -600% because the maximum value of P_{kr} for each mode is 100%.

Furthermore, the inequality constraints of the problem shown in Eq. (11) also need to be fulfilled.

$$\begin{aligned} g_r(\{X\}) &= p - \max(P_{kr}) \leq 0; \quad k = r = 1, 2, \dots, 6 \\ g_7(\{X\}) &= 7 \leq \omega_r \leq 47 \\ g_8 &= \Omega_{r+1}(\{X\}) - \Omega_r(\{X\}) \geq 2 \\ g_9 &= T_m^j(w) = 20 \log[H_m^j(w)] < -30 \text{ dB} \\ g_9 &= -300 \leq X_1 \leq 50 \\ g_{10} &= -250 \leq Y_1 \leq 50 \\ g_{11} &= -150 \leq Z_1 \leq 50 \\ g_{12} &= -300 \leq X_2 \leq 50 \\ g_{13} &= 0050 \leq Y_2 \leq 250 \\ g_{14} &= -150 \leq Z_2 \leq 50 \\ g_{15} &= 100 \leq S_{1x} \leq 600 \\ g_{16} &= 100 \leq S_{1y} \leq 600 \\ g_{17} &= 100 \leq S_{1z} \leq 600 \\ g_{18} &= 100 \leq S_{2x} \leq 600 \\ g_{18} &= 100 \leq S_{2y} \leq 600 \\ g_{20} &= 100 \leq S_{2z} \leq 600 \\ g_{21} &= 100 \leq S_{3x} \leq 600 \\ g_{22} &= 100 \leq S_{3y} \leq 600 \\ g_{23} &= 100 \leq S_{3z} \leq 600 \\ g_{24} &= 100 \leq S_{4x} \leq 600 \\ g_{25} &= 100 \leq S_{4y} \leq 600 \\ g_{26} &= 100 \leq S_{4z} \leq 600 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Here, p is the lower limit for the modal purity that is required in the project. In this work a modal purity p of 85% for each degree of freedom is chased as design criteria.

There are another two constraints related to the eigenvalues. These constraints are the functions $g_7(\{X\})$, which limits the frequency range of the rigid body modes between 7 Hz and 47 Hz, and the $g_8(\{X\})$ which requires that the separation of the frequencies of the modes must be greater or equal to 2 Hz. The frequency range and the frequency separation were extracted from benchmark studies of the vehicles on the market.

The constrained function $g_8(\{X\}) (T_m^j(w))$ is the module of the transmissibility function $H_m^j(w)$ converted to the dB scale. The isolation of -30 dB is used as the criteria of mount isolation, which corresponds to a reduction of about 32 times, here m represents the mount number and j represents the direction x, y or z.

Since the mathematical model of the rigid body mode is defined, it is possible to find the best modal purity by solving the optimization problem defined in Eq. (23).

The changes in the mount position can be highly sensible for modal purity and implies in strong modifications of this criteria. To have a controlled and predictable change on the project, optimization approaches can be used to overcome and predict downsides in changes like that. Figure 1 shows the flowchart of the optimization process.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the optimization process.

Once the design criteria of Eq. (23) is met the optimization process is completed.

III. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the optimization considering different initial positions. Three different initial conditions (initial Condition 1, 2 and 3) changing the initial position of the mounts will be done with the objective to verify whether the algorithm can meet a local minimum more than once with different vector $\{X\}$. Whether this is the case the problem is pointing to different combination of the mount position meeting the constrained and the objective function criteria.

3.1 Results of Different Optimizations of the Motor Mount Project

Table 1 shows the comparison of the six natural frequencies obtained from the optimization results for conditions 1, 2 and 3, these three conditions come from a different start point of mount location and show that depending on where the algorithm start different results can be obtained. The frequency criterion of the restriction functions were defined to be greater than 7 Hz and smaller than 47 Hz.

Table 1: Comparison of the natural frequencies of the conditions 1, 2 and 3.

Frequency	Condition 1 (Hz)	Condition 2 (Hz)	Condition 3 (Hz)
f ₁	10.94	11.75	11.49
f ₂	13.37	13.49	13.74
f ₃	16.24	15.90	16.51
f ₄	18.39	17.38	19.10
f ₅	22.73	22.26	23.26
f ₆	31.01	33.90	31.11

Table 2 shows the comparison of the modal purity per DOF for the conditions 1, 2 and 3. The constraint functions of modal purity required a modal purity greater than 85%.

Table 2: Comparison of the modal purity of each DOF for conditions 1, 2 and 3.

Modal Purity X (%)				Modal Purity Y (%)		
DOF	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
f ₁	0	0	0	97	87	91
f ₂	85	99	100	0	1	0
f ₃	0	0	0	2	1	0
f ₄	1	0	0	0	0	0
f ₅	0	0	0	1	11	9
f ₆	14	0	0	0	0	0
Modal Purity Z (%)				Modal Purity RX (%)		
DOF	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
f ₁	2	0	0	0	1	0
f ₂	0	0	0	1	0	0
f ₃	92	9	97	0	89	0
f ₄	0	90	0	99	10	100
f ₅	5	0	0	0	0	0
f ₆	0	1	3	0	0	0
Modal Purity RY (%)				Modal Purity RZ (%)		
DOF	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
f ₁	0	0	9	0	11	0
f ₂	14	0	0	0	0	0
f ₃	0	0	0	6	0	3
f ₄	0	1	0	0	0	0
f ₅	0	0	91	94	89	0
f ₆	86	99	0	0	0	97

Table 3 shows the comparison of the transmissibility of mounts 1, 2, 3 and 4 in each direction for the conditions 1, 2 and 3. The constraint functions of transmissibility required a transmissibility smaller than -30dB.

Table 3: Comparison of the transmissibility of mounts 1, 2, 3 and 4 for the conditions 1,2 and 3.

		Transmissibility Mount 1			Transmissibility Mount 2		
Coordinate	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	
X	-31.70	-31.69	-31.36	-31.67	-31.69	-31.36	
Y	-34.81	-34.44	-34.82	-34.82	-34.44	-34.84	
Z	-30.06	-29.80	-30.09	-29.86	-29.80	-30.06	
		Transmissibility Mount 3			Transmissibility Mount 4		
Coordinate	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	
X	-31.83	-31.78	-32.19	-31.83	-31.78	-32.19	
Y	-33.98	-34.05	-33.89	-33.92	-34.04	-33.81	
Z	-29.87	-29.85	-30.15	-29.77	-29.84	-30.14	

Table 4 shows the comparison of the position and stiffness of mounts 1, 2, 3 and 4 for conditions 1, 2 and 3. The table shows how the positions and stiffness change.

Table 4: Comparison of the position and stiffness of mounts 1, 2, 3 and 4 for the Conditions 1, 2 and 3.

Position and Mount Stiffness Optimization Mount 1				
Variable	Coordinate	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
Position (mm)	X	-140	-246	-200
	Y	-204	-117	-223
	Z	-73	-46	-35
Stiffness (N/mm)	X	400.21	400.60	416.74
	Y	185.04	193.26	184.81
	Z	485.97	501.11	484.51
Position and Mount Stiffness Optimization Mount 2				
Variable	Coordinate	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
Position (mm)	X	-181	-246	-193
	Y	188	153	224
	Z	-66	-43	-15
Stiffness (N/mm)	X	401.75	400.74	416.53
	Y	184.69	193.26	184.25
	Z	497.67	501.44	486.08
Position and Mount Stiffness Optimization Mount 3				
Variable	Coordinate	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
Position (mm)	X	319	319	319
	Y	-220	-220	-220
	Z	11	11	11
Stiffness (N/mm)	X	393.97	396.18	377.57
	Y	204.00	202.21	205.99
	Z	496.90	498.42	480.86
Position and Mount Stiffness Optimization Mount 4				
Variable	Coordinate	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
Position (mm)	X	319	319	319
	Y	220	220	220

	Z	11	11	11
Stiffness (N/mm)	X	393.98	396.18	377.56
	Y	205.44	202.46	207.90
	Z	503.22	498.87	481.09

Table 5 shows the magnitude of the positions of the mounts 1 and 2, with the three different conditions assessed. This table indicates how the magnitude of length of the bracket mount can be explored during the optimization process. This can be used to, for example, optimize local resonance frequencies of the bracket that might be causing problems on transmissibility.

Table 5: Comparison of the magnitude of each position of mounts 1 and 2 for Conditions 1, 2 and 3.

Vector Sum Optimization Mount 1			
Variable	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
Lenght (mm)	258	277	302
Vector Sum Optimization Mount 2			
Variable	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
Lenght (mm)	269	293	296

This kind of result where the dimension of the mount bracket can be explored is useful to stiffen the bracket and consequently shift the bracket's natural frequency away from the critical operating range of the motor [13]. Once the mount bracket dimension is optimized there are other methods that can be used focusing on the bracket topology [14] or even using mounts with active control [15].

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this study was to optimize the design of a vehicle mount by incorporating the rigid body mode and isolation performance as key technical criteria, aiming to develop a high-performance vibration isolation system.

For this purpose, an analytical rigid body mode model with generic inputs like the number of mounts, mount inclination, mount position, mount stiffness, and the loss factor of the mount was built.

The constraint functions were formulated based on the limits of mount position, stiffness, natural frequencies of the rigid body modes, modal purity, and transmissibility.

After setting all these constraints, the PDLB interior-point algorithm was applied for three different initial conditions of position keeping the same initial stiffness condition. For all three conditions of optimization, the objective functions were satisfied resulting in high modal purity (higher than 85% for each DOF) and high isolation performance. It was observed that for the Condition 2 the constraint of frequency separation of 2 Hz between the modes was not met. An interesting outcome observed from the optimization process was that the algorithm primarily focused on adjusting the mount position, with only minimal variations in the mount stiffness. The isolation also met the performance with an overall transmissibility performance around -30 dB or more depending on the considered direction.

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